

Article

Extraction and purification of protein from orange seeds

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Abstract: Orange is a nutrient rich Fruit. The research on Orange showed that it can be used to treat many diseases or the daily intake of orange extracts prevents the development of many diseases besides this aspect all parts of Orange are rich in protein contents thus used as protein source in many developing countries. The proteins of Orange seed have many useful applications. The present work describes extraction and purification of protein from Orange seed. The crude proteins were extracted by using six extraction solutions and the purification of protein from the crude extract was done using ammonium sulfate precipitation method. The purity of the protein was analyzed by SDS-PAGE. The quantification of extracted protein was done with spectrophotometer. The results showed that the pure protein was obtained with 50% ammonium sulfate saturation. The pure protein was further characterized for its antibacterial activity. The protein did not kill the bacterial strains which were used in this study indicating that this protein is not antibacterial against these particular strains.

Keywords: Orange, protein, saturation, bacteria,

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1.Introduction

Orange fruit is originated from South East Asia. Orange fruit is one of the most extensively consumed fruits in the world. It is consumed all over the world as tremendous source of vitamin C, a powerful natural antioxidant that builds the body immune system [1]. Orange fruit is a hesperidium. Orange is a kind of berry that ranges extensively in size, colour, shape, and juice quality. Fruits are globose to ovoid in shape. The main production regions of oranges are found in the

United States of America (led by Brazil, Mexico, and Argentina), the Mediterranean basin (led by Spain, Italy, Egypt, and Turkey), and the South and East Asian regions (led by China, India, Pakistan and Japan)[2]. Orange fruit is grown in all four provinces of Pakistan Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Baluchistan [3]. Oranges are popular variety, which is eaten more by the community. Mostly, Sweet Oranges were grown firstly in the Asia. That spread slowly to whole Asia and become popular in very short time all across the world. The topmost citrus species used for commercial fruit tree farming business are mandarin (*Citrus reticulata*), acid lime (*Citrus aurantifolia*), & sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*). Besides, this there also several types of oranges, used for farming. The flowers of oranges have fragrance sweetness, because of which attract numerous honey bees. Apart from being grown as commercial fruit tree farming, oranges are also grown in a container, pots, or in the garden of the house. Commercial orange farming is very flourishing & profitable if cultivated with good farm management skills and proper care. Note that Orange trees are very prone to numbers of pest, insects, and diseases. So, care and management play an important role in the production of orange cultivation. The climate is the most important parameter for selecting the location of an orange field. The climate determines the success of orange farm and the quality of citrus fruits, while soil and water determine the productivity of orange trees. Cold is the most important enemy of an orange tree. Temperatures below 32° F (0 ° C) are dangerous for the orange tree, especially when maintained for long periods. High temperatures may also prove critical to the productivity of trees. High-speed and cold winds can also cause damage to trees, vegetation reduction, loss of fruits and deterioration of their quality [4]. Date palm is considered the oldest fruit tree in the world. It has been cultivated in North Africa and the Middle East for millennia, although the exact origin of date palm has not been verified [11] Some reports cite that it has been used since 4000 BC in Mesopotamia and by the Egyptians since 2000-3000 BC [12] Either the Indian date palm (*P. sylvestris*) or the African date palm may have been the progenitor of *Phoenix dactylifera* [13]. Dates play an important role in the social life of the people who live in these regions both in their diet and medicinally for treating e.g. obesity [14]. There are more than 2000 different cultivars of date palm known worldwide but only a few of them have been used for their agricultural productivity and fruit quality Botanically, date palm is a monocotyledonous plant that belongs to the *Arecaceae* (previously known as *Palmaceae* or *Palmae*) family which contains 200 genera and more than 2000 species[15] There are many species of the genus *Phoenix*, but the species of *Phoenix dactylifera* is the one most cultivated for their edible fruits, whereas other species produce fruits which can be used by animals and birds[16].

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Dicotyledons
Sub class	Sapindales
Order	Rosidae
Family	Rutaccae
Sub family	Aurantoideae
Genera	Citrus
Sub genera	Papeda
Species	Sinensis

Table. 1: Taxonomic classification

Country	Name
U.K	Narinch, Narindz, Narinjh
Holland	Appelsien
France	Oranger, Sanguine
Italy	Arancia, Aranciodolce
Germany	Apfelsine
Japan	Orenji, Orenzi
Spain	Naranja, Naranjodulce
Pakistan	Mosambi, Sangtra, Kinnow

Table. 2: Common Name

Oranges are rich in vitamin C and their seeds inclusive. The vitamin C in oranges and their seeds is a powerful antioxidant that profits the body and the health. People extract oil from orange seeds and this can serve as a cleaning product, which provides a fresh scent as well as cleaning and de-greasing abilities [17]. Limonoid and limonoid glycosides are citrus compounds that we can find in the seeds, peel, and fruit of citrus. They are effective against human breast cancer cells. Orange seed oil also is a great conditioning agent when used in hair care products. Oranges and their seeds also contain numerous antioxidants which protect the body from free radicals. Orange seeds can also be ground into powder for use in cosmetics and skin conditioning products as well. The use of orange seed oil in chemical industries for the production of soap, perfumes, candles, lubricant, flavoring and insecticides has been justified[5]. Orange seed oil contains palmitic, oleic and linoleic acids. Palmitic acid facilitates long-term storage of energy in human cells. Orange seeds provide a high-protein residue which is suitable for human and animal consumption [6]. Normal sweet oranges are diploids, with nine pairs of chromosomes and a predictable genome size of ~367 Mb [7]. Germination times can be as long as six to eight weeks. Oranges has many blooming periods throughout the year depending on many factors such as climate or soils, but the best seasons for it to bloom are between spring and fall. They tend to flower and fruit during periods of comparatively abundant rainfall and become dormant if a pronounced drier period occurs during the summer [18]. Only a small proportion of flowers will produce fruit because the tree will drop many of its flowers or young oranges so it can support the ones it does keep. Oranges take between three and five years to start flowering and five and eighteen months to develop the fruit. The secret to grow orange is sun exposure and water, needs a minimum of six hours a day in the sun. Lack of less sun will lead to smaller oranges of poor quality. They will continue to become sweeter on the tree but that process stops as soon as you pick them [19]. Oranges do not continue to ripen off the tree. It is best to harvest your ripe fruits before the heat of summer arrives because the heat may harm the fruits and stress the entire tree. Oranges start to grow flower buds in early winter [20]. They develop slowly through the late winter into spring, many flowers are produced that up to 99 percent of them fall off without setting fruit. Many of the small fruits fall off during the "June drop" period in late May and June. The remaining oranges continue to grow, maturing seven to 15 months after fruit set, depending on the variety and growing conditions. Fruit color doesn't always show ripeness. Some oranges develop some green on the skin, called re-greening, due to cooler winter temperatures, but they are ready to harvest. Pollination occurs between winter and spring depending on latitude and elevation [8].

2 .Research Methodology

2.1 Extraction of proteins

Six different types of extraction buffers used to extract the proteins which are as follow:

1. **Tris-HCl (0.01 M):** To prepare 50 ml of extraction buffer dissolved 0.061 g of Tris-HCl in 50 ml of distilled water. Adjust the pH of buffer at 8.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic sketch of methodology of the Project

2. **Na-acetate (0.01 M):** To prepare 50 ml of extraction buffer dissolved 0.041 g of Na-acetate in 50 ml of distilled water. Adjust the pH of buffer at 4.0.

3. Calcium chloride (0.1 M): To prepare 50 ml of extraction solution dissolved 0.55 g of calcium chloride in 50 ml of distilled water.

4. Distilled water: 50 ml of distilled water also used as extraction solvent.

5. Sodium chloride (0.1 M): To prepare 50 ml of extraction solution dissolved 0.55 g of Sodium chloride in 50 ml of distilled water.

6. Potassium chloride (0.1M): To prepare 50 ml of extraction solution dissolved 0.55 g of Potassium chloride in 50 ml of distilled water.

All these extraction buffers/solutions were stored at 4°C for further use in extraction procedure.

2.1.1. Seeds

Fresh ripened seeds of orange were used in this project.

2.1.2. Procedure

The seed was removed and takes out the seed kernel, as the protein is extracting in this experiment from the pods of *orange*. The seed was completely grind using liquid Nitrogen and convert into powder form with the help of spatula. The powder was suspended in 5ml of each extraction buffer, left for 30 minutes in shaking incubator at 22 °C. The dissolved materials were centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 15 minutes. Filter the supernatant using filter paper. The supernatant of each mixture was transfer in falcon tubes and stored it at 4 °C. The supernatant containing protein was used for further experiments.

2.1. Precipitation of protein

Mix the small amount of supernatant of all six mixtures (extraction buffer + pods) in which extracted protein is present the resulting mixture called as pool. Use this pool for Ammonium sulfate precipitation. Take 2 ml of pool in each of six falcon tubes to make different ammonium sulfate for different saturations.

S.no	Saturations	Amount of ammonium sulfate
1.	20%	0.21g
2.	30%	0.11g
3.	40%	0.112g
4.	50%	0.116g
5.	60%	0.12g

Table. 3: Different saturations of ammonium sulfate

Solid ammonium sulfate was added to 10 ml of supernatant as given in above table to make 20% saturation. The solution was then stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 400 rpm without heat and was left for 30 minutes for precipitation of proteins and then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. The supernatant was removed and the pellet was mixed in 30 µl of Tris-HCl buffer pH 8.0 and stored at 4°C. The process was repeated for 30%, 40%, 50%, 60% saturations [9].

2.3. Quantification of protein:

To determine protein concentration, proceeding towards electrophoresis. Measuring protein concentration involves absorbance in the UV range or staining the protein with dye.

2.3.1 Samples of six extraction solutions:

The concentration of protein in pellets was checked with spectrophotometer. The lid factor 10 is used to quantify the samples. Tris-HCl buffer is used as blank as the pellets were suspended in the Tris-HCl buffer.

2.3.2. Pellets of Ammonium sulfate precipitation:

The concentration of protein in pellets was checked with spectrophotometer. The lid factor 10 is used to quantify the samples. Tris-HCl buffer is used as blank as the pellets were suspended in the Tris-HCl buffer.

2.4. SDS-PAGE:

2.4.1. 1x Electrode buffer:

Chemicals	Quantity
25 mM Tris-base	3.9 g
192 mM glycine	14.4 g
0.1% SDS	1g

Table . 4: The following reagents were dissolved in 1 liter of distilled water to make 1x electrode buffer.

2.4.2. Sample buffer (Non-Reducing)

The following components are added to make sample buffer but β -mercaptoethanol is not added in the whole volume. The final volume is 10 ml.

Chemicals	Quantity
0.06 M Tris-HCl	1.275 ml
10% SDS	2 ml
10% glycerol	1 ml
0.025% Bromophenol blue	0.25 ml
Distilled water	4.8 ml

Table. 5 : Chemical composition of non-reducing sample buffer

2.4.3. Sample buffer (Reducing)

Take 950 μ l of non-reducing buffer and add 50ul of β -mercaptoethanol in it to make it reducing buffer.

2.4.4. Staining solution

For staining of gel the staining solution was made by adding the following chemicals.

The final volume of solution was 100 ml.

1. 10% Acetic acid
2. 50% Methanol
3. Coomassie Brilliant blue = 0.4g

2.4.5. De-staining solution

For the de-staining of gel 50% methanol solution is used.

2.6. Polyacrylamide Gel

A collective technique for separating proteins by electrophoresis uses irregular polyacrylamide gel and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) to denature the proteins.

2.6.1. Separating Gel

The concentration of the gel is 15% and the final volume is 11ml. The chemical composition of gel is as follow:

Chemicals	Quantity
Distilled water	2.47 ml
30% Acrylamide + Bis-acrylamide	5.5ml
1.5 M Tris, pH 8.8	2.75 ml
10% SDS	110 μ l
10% APS	110 μ l
TEMED	11 μ l

Table. 6 : Chemical composition of separating gel

Leave the gel for 25 minutes for solidification. After the gel becomes solidify pour it on solidified separating gel and insert the combs in it to make wells for loading samples.

2.7. Procedure

Two gels were run for:

- 1) Six extraction buffer samples
- 2) Pellets of ammonium sulfate saturations

2.7.1. Sample preparation

To prepare the samples for Gel following steps are taken:

1. Take 30 μ l of each sample in Eppendorf tubes.
2. Add 10 μ l of sample buffer in each sample.
3. Give the heat shock to samples at 99 $^{\circ}$ C for 4 minutes
4. Centrifuge the samples for 5 min at 5000 rpm.

2.7.2. Gel run

1. To run the gel firstly fills the tank with 1x electrode buffer.
2. Load the samples in wells.
3. Run the gel at 100 volts for 25 minutes first.
4. When the first run completed set the gel at 120 volts for 120 minutes.

2.7.3. Staining of Gel

The gel was placed in staining solution for 25 minutes so the proteins bands become stained properly.

2.7.4. De-Staining of Gel

Transfer the gel in de-staining solution and leave it for overnight.

2.7. Molecular weight of protein through SDS-PAGE

For calculating the molecular weight of the protein. Calculated the migration distance of every band presented in the gel from top. Use a ruler to calculate. Calculate the first band from the starting, did same thing for each and other band of the gel and get values of every band migration distance. Then the Rf values were calculated. Opened excel and calculated log molecular weight for all the migration distances. Entered the formula, calculate log molecular weight, got the values for every band. Now made the scattered plot (The standard Curve). Selected data for the curve then added the series, on x-axis migration distance was shown and on y-axis log molecular weight. Added trend line and trend element. Draw trend line and then done format selection. Measured the distance in cm. Insert the textbox for further captions. Estimated the molecular weight for the pure band of protein. Use equation for the molecular weight, type equation R values of the graph. Added the pure band migration distance in R values of curve. Now calculate the molecular weight in log. The protein single band was appeared below the 60 kDa of protein marker. The estimated molecular weight of the protein is 62.78kDa.

2.8. Characterization of protein

2.8.1. Antibacterial Assay

Culture medium and inoculum preparation

LB Agar was used for checking antibacterial activity of pure protein from seed of *orange* against *Enterococcus durans* and *Enterococcus lectin*, and bacteria obtained from milk and yogurt (dairy products). The microbial strains were cultured in 5ml of LB Broth in 2 falcon tube in laminar flow hood. These falcon tubes were incubated at 37°C for bacterial growth for 24 hours. This bacterial growth in LB Broth was used for streaking onto the agar plates for antimicrobial test.

Agar well diffusion assay

By the Agar well diffusion assay the antibacterial activity of the pure protein was determined [16]. 5.25 g of LB agar was dissolved in 150 ml of distilled water and autoclaved at 121 C for 15 minutes. Allow the medium to cool and then equally poured into the 4 petri plates and leave it for 30 minutes to solidify. After this, it is inoculated with the culture using sterile cotton swabs. The wells are created using sterile agar borer and filled the wells by adding 500µl of pure protein and were incubated at 37 °C for 12–24 h. The protein having antimicrobial activity, inhibit the microbial growth and the clear zones were formed. The zone of inhibition was measured in millimeters.

3. Result and Discussion:

3.1. Extraction of proteins

The seed of *orange* was grinded and the powder seed coat was treated with six extraction solution which is: Tris-HCl pH 8.0 (buffer), Na-acetate pH 4.0 (buffer), CaCl₂ solution, distilled water, Sodium chloride and Potassium chloride. The resulting crude protein extract was centrifuged and the supernatant was analyzed by SDS-PAGE (Fig.1). The 15% Polyacrylamide gel was prepared for the analysis of presence of proteins in each extracts from six extraction buffers/solution. The gel revealed different protein bands ranging in molecular weight from 120 kDa to 10 kDa (Fig.1). This shows that the proteins of different molecular weight and of different nature are present in seed of *Orange*. But the mostly clear bands of proteins appeared have low molecular weight ranging from 20 kDa to 50 kDa these results showed that the proteins present in seed coat of

Orange are of low molecular weight. The protein was present in Tris-HCl buffer means that protein was most soluble in basic solution as this buffer has pH of 8.8.

Fig 1 : 15% SDS gel with proteins of orange which are extracted with four buffers. M: Molecular weight of markers (kDa), 1; Sodium Chloride buffer sample 2 ; Potassium Chloride buffer sample 3 ; Distilled water buffer sample, 4; Calcium chloride buffer sample, 5; Tris-HCL buffer sample 6; Na-Acetate buffer sample.

3.2. Precipitation of protein

The extracted proteins with Tris-HCl pH 8.0 (buffer), solutions were pooled and the ammonium sulfate precipitation technique was applied for purification of protein of interest. The pellets of different saturations of ammonium sulfate were obtained which are 20%, 30%, 40%, 50% and 60%. These pellets were analyzed on SDS-PAGE to check the presence of purified protein of interest (Fig 3.2).

Fig 2: 15%gel for pellets of ammonium sulfate saturations containing proteins of *Orange* seed coat **M:** Molecular weight markers (kDa) 1: 20% pellets, 2: 30% pellet, 3: 40% pellet, 4: 50% pellet, 5: 60% pellet.

3.3. Molecular weight of protein through SDS-PAGE

For calculating the molecular weight of the protein .Calculated the migration distance of every band presented in the gel from top. Use a ruler to calculate. Calculate the first band from the starting, did same thing for each and other band

of the gel and get values of every band migration distance. Opened excel and calculated log molecular weight. Entered the formula, calculate log molecular weight, got the values for every band. Now made the scattered plot. Selected data for the curve then added the series on x-axis migration distance was shown and on y-axis log molecular weight. Added trend line and trend element. Draw trend line and then done format selection. Measured the distance in cm. Insert the textbox for further captions. Now estimated the molecular weight for the pure band of protein. Use equation for the molecular weight, type equation R values of the graph. Now calculate the molecular weight in log. The protein single band was appeared to be at 60 kDa. The molecular weight of the protein is 62.78 kDa.

Figure 3. Molecular weight standard curve for SDS-PAGE

The estimated molecular weight of the pure protein of Seed is 62.78 kDa.

Figure 4 : Gel for molecular weight determination

3.4. Quantification of protein content

3.4.1 Six extraction samples

The quantification of protein content in extracts was done by using spectrophotometer. The crude extract of protein obtained by using four extraction buffers and the protein content in pellets of Ammonium sulfate was quantified on spectrophotometer (Table 3.1). The concentration varies from buffer to buffer. The high protein concentration is present in Tris-HCL which shows that the protein of seed of Orange *is* more soluble in the basic solution.

S.no	Extraction buffers	Concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{ul}$
1	Tris-HCl	3.768
2	Distilled water	2.675
3	Na-acetate	1.613
4	Calcium chloride	3.617
5	Potassium chloride	1.513
6	Calcium chloride	1.214

Table . 7: Concentration of protein in 6 extracted samples

The graphical representation of concentration of protein in four extraction buffers is as follow:

Figure 4: Concentration of extracted protein in different buffers

3.4.2. Quantification of protein in Ammonium sulfate pellets

The concentration of purified protein in pellets of different saturations of ammonium sulfate which were obtained by the precipitation experiment was quantified on spectrophotometer. The concentration of proteins was high in the pellets of low saturations as the saturation of ammonium sulfate increases the protein concentration decreased.

S.no	Pellets	Concentration in µg/µl
1	30%	6.762
2	40%	13.8
3	50%	13.5
4	60%	11.0

Table 8 : Relative concentration of protein in different pellets with ammonium sulfate precipitation.

Figure 5 : The graphical representation for the comparison of concentration of protein in pellets of different saturations.

3.5. Antibacterial Activity

To check the antibacterial activity of protein of interest the agar well diffusion assay was done. Two strains were treated with the protein which is *Enterococcus durans* (S2C), *Enterococcus lectin* (R13), and the bacterial culture grown from the dairy products. The protein was added in positive control plates. No zone of inhibition was produced in any control plate (Fig. 3.6 A-D). The results showed that protein did not kill any bacterial strain nor it inhibits the growth of any bacterial strain.

Figure 6 : (A) *Enterococcus lectin* R13 (control), (B) Positive Control (R13), (C) *Enterococcus durans* S2C, (D) Positive control S2C

Extraction of protein from all six buffers revealed that the concentration varies from buffer to buffer but the high protein concentration is present in Tris-HCL which shows that the protein of seed of Orange is more soluble in the basic solution as the pH of the buffer is 8.8. The pure bands of protein observed in 50% saturation of ammonium sulfate, which means that at this saturation the protein is much concentrated and present in pure form. (Lane 4, Figure 3.2).

The molecular weight of the pure protein was calculated. Calculated the molecular weight in log through SDS-PAGE. The protein single band was appeared to be near at 60 kDa according to the protein marker. The estimated molecular weight of the protein through SDS-PAGE is 62.78 kDa. The pure band migration distance added in R value of Standard curve.

The concentration of ammonium sulfate increases the concentration of precipitated protein decreases which shows that protein is less soluble in the presence of low salt concentration and can be purified in more amounts but when the concentration of ammonium sulfate increases the solubility of protein also increases thus the precipitation rate become low. The pure proteins were obtained at high concentration (50% saturation).

For testing its antibacterial activity, two strains were treated with the protein which is *Enterococcus durans* (S2C), *Enterococcus lectin* (R13). The protein was added in positive control plates. No zone of inhibition was produced in any control plate (Figure 3.6 A-D). The results showed that this flocculating protein is not an antibacterial protein as flocculating protein didn't show any activity against these particular strains.

References:

- [1] Etebu, E., & Nwauzoma, A. B. (2014a). A REVIEW ON SWEET ORANGE (CITRUS SINENSIS L Osbeck): HEALTH, DISEASES AND MANAGEMENT. American Journal of Research Communication, 2(2). Retrieved from http://www.usa-journals.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/Etebu_Vol22.pdf
- [2] Musasa, S. T., Musundire, R., Mashingaidze, A. B., & Makuza, S. M. (2015). A preliminary study of the orange (*Citrus sinensis*) fruit value-chain in Chimanimani Rural District, Zimbabwe. African Journal of Agricultural Research, 10(35), 3507–3516. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJAR2015.10041>
- [3] Mohar, T. A., Abbas, M. M., Awan, M. Z., Javed, M. A., & Farooq, A. (2011). PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT SWEET ORANGE VARIETIES UNDER FAISALABAD CONDITIONS. Journal of Agricultural Research, 49(3).
- [4] Hume, H. H. (1926). The cultivation of citrus fruits. Macmillan And Co., Limited; London
- [5] Jahn, O. L. (1973). Inflorescence Types and Fruiting Patterns in Hamlin and Valencia Oranges and Marsh Grapefruit. American Journal of Botany, 60(7), 663. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2441444>
- [6] Jorge, N., Carolina, A., Silva, D., & Aranha, C. P. M. (2016). Antioxidant activity of oils extracted from orange (*Citrus sinensis*) seeds. An Acad Bras Cienc Annals of the Brazilian Academy of Sciences, 88(882), 951–958. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201620140562>
- [7] Xu, Q., Chen, L.-L., Ruan, X., Chen, D., Zhu, A., Chen, C., ... Ruan, Y. (2013). The draft genome of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*). Nature Genetics, 45(1), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.2472>

- [8]Wootton-Beard, P. C., & Ryan, L. (2011). Improving public health?: The role of antioxidant-rich fruit and vegetable beverages. *Food Research International*, 44(10), 3135–3148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2011.09.015>
- [9]Burgess, R. R. (2009). Protein precipitation techniques. *Methods in enzymology*, 463, 331342.
- [10]American Society for Horticultural Science., K. T., Obreza, T. A., & Scholberg, J. M. S. (2007). *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science* (Vol. 132). [American Society for Horticultural Science]. Retrieved from <http://journal.ashspublications.org/content/132/2/262.short>
- [11]Angel Gil-Izquierdo, Maria I. Gil, and, & Ferreres*, F. (2002). Effect of Processing Techniques at Industrial Scale on Orange Juice Antioxidant and Beneficial Health Compounds. <https://doi.org/10.1021/JF020162+>
- [12]Asian Network for Scientific Information., N. ,Hil. F. R. S. M. (Pakistan))Karacali, I. (2001). *Journal of biological sciences*. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* (Pakistan). ANSInet. Retrieved from <http://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search.do?recordID=PK2005000232>
- [13]Butelli, E., Licciardello, C., Zhang, Y., Liu, J., Mackay, S., Bailey, P., ... Martin, C. (2012). Retrotransposons control fruit-specific, cold-dependent accumulation of anthocyanins in blood oranges. *The Plant Cell*, 24(3), 1242–1255. <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.111.095232>
- [14]Cardile, V., Frasca, G., Rizza, L., Rapisarda, P., & Bonina, F. (2010). Antiinflammatory effects of a red orange extract in human keratinocytes treated with interferon-gamma and histamine. *Phytotherapy Research*, 24(3), 414–418. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ptr.2973>
- [15]Ghaedi, A. M., Ghaedi, M., & Karami, P. (2015). Comparison of ultrasonic with stirrer performance for removal of sunset yellow (SY) by activated carbon prepared from wood of orange tree: Artificial neural network modeling. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 138, 789–799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SAA.2014.11.019>
- [16]Jayaprakasha, G. K., Girennavar, B., & Patil, B. S. (2008). Radical scavenging activities of Rio Red grapefruits and Sour orange fruit extracts in different in vitro model systems. *Bioresource Technology*, 99(10), 4484–4494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2007.07.067>
- [17]Machado, M. A., Coletta Filho, H. D., Targon, M. L. P. N., & Pompeu, J. (1995). Genetic relationship of Mediterranean mandarins (*Citrus deliciosa* Tenore) using RAPD markers. *Euphytica*, 92(3), 321–326. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00037115>

- [18]Mikhail, E., & El-Zeftawi, B. (1979). Effect of soil types and rootstocks on root distribution, chemical composition of leaves and yield of valencia oranges. *Australian Journal of Soil Research*, 17(2), 335. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR9790335>
- [19]Nisperos-Carriedo, M. O., & Shaw, P. E. (1990). Comparison of volatile flavor components in fresh and processed orange juices. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 38(4), 1048–1052. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf00094a029>
- [20]Rech Franke, S. I., Guecheva, T. N., Henriques, J. A. P., & Prá, D. (2013). Orange Juice and Cancer Chemoprevention. *Nutrition and Cancer*, 65(7), 943–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01635581.2013.817594>

